

INFLUENCE OF ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS ON THE PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE

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The healing powers of nature are known to almost all people. In addition, lectures, talks, special broadcasts and shows are conducted on water, air, sun and environmental ecology. Mass media are constantly covering natural landscapes in the republic's territories, experiences in using them for health, and events. Based on these, some arguments can be made about the scientific foundations related to the healing powers of nature.

Air, sunlight, and water are used as means of physical education in the form of healing forces of nature in the process of physical education. Living conditions and environment force a person to live and create material wealth in different conditions. It is important to get used to it and be ready for it. Therefore, the gift of nature - air, water, sunlight - is the main means of increasing human working capacity and strengthening health.

We know that most of the teaching processes of the students of higher educational institutions are conducted in the auditoriums and they do not exercise enough during the day. The process of physical education is the main solution for this. By engaging in physical education, the body of students gets enough exposure to the cold and hot air of nature, sunlight, and strengthens their health through physical exercises. The process of physical education is effective when performing physical exercises in the open air, under sunlight, using water, etc. Bathing, sunbathing, hot and cold weather and physical exercises have different effects on the human body. Systematic use of these tools during training is important.

The work should be organized in such a way that the problem of developing a scientifically based system of using the healing forces of nature in all regions and regions should be solved, taking into account the geographical, climatic and ecological conditions of our beloved Republic. For example, if sunlight is used separately from 10.00 to 12.00 and from 16.00 to 17.30 without taking into account age, gender and other individual characteristics, its effect will be different. We must not forget that neglecting the norm of physical exercises, the total amount of load, the intensity of the exercise will lead to negative results in the use of the healing forces of nature.

The theoretical knowledge of sunbathing, water exercise and their systematic use, change of air, quick adaptation of the body to hot and cold, sudden changes, is very effective for the participants. Comprehensive training, combining natural factors with various physical exercises, increases the body's ability to resist the negative effects of the external environment.

The effect of training achieved in the process of physical education is "portable", that is, it is manifested in other activities of a person (mainly, labor, military service) and increases the practicality of physical education. In addition, it strengthens mental and willpower qualities. In particular, tasks such as swaying, shaking, enduring excessive stress, and quickly adapting to the state of weightlessness are easily solved.

According to the results of science, theoretical and practical experiments in medicine, biology, chemistry, physiology, theory of physical culture, sports activities (training) and other fields, the influence of air is manifested in the following cases:

1. During normal sitting and standing, breathing is not noticeable, but as a result of certain movements (fast and strong), breathing becomes faster and deeper. Air reaches the lungs and old air (carbonic anhydrite) is pushed out. This, in turn, ensures vitality (blood circulation, heartbeat, normal functioning of nerves, etc.). The need for air increases as a result of performing various physical works and physical exercises. Clean and normal (hot and cold) air is necessary for this. Accordingly, it is necessary to perform exercises and work.

2. Breathing can become difficult and stop due to various reasons. In such cases, the mouth is forcibly opened, a cloth or other object is placed between the teeth, the tongue is pulled forward, and the mouth is blown. Also, by pressing the chest several times, it activates the lung function for breathing. This method often gives positive results in life. Therefore, the necessity of air for life is quickly known in such cases.

3. Depending on the physical condition and development of the human body, the throat adapts to hot and cold. It is clear that especially young children, the elderly and patients are prone to colds and sore throats in cold weather. For this reason, it is necessary to know the specific movement of the house and outside air, and to use them purposefully. In this way, it is necessary to carry young children in the open air, to play, to walk, to get used to drinking cold water and various drinks, and to train them.

Under the influence of natural factors of water, sun, air, strengthening the health of students, training and increasing the body's resistance to diseases;

Carrying out physical education classes in fresh air as much as possible or organizing sports halls with fresh air;

Directing students to water treatments, swimming and bathing activities, and sunbathing activities.

Due to the fact that the body has developed its own adaptation feature, we can train our body and strengthen our health with the help of environmental factors. Also, conducting physical exercises and physical training sessions in the open air had a very good effect on the body.

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